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Differentiation of rice varieties cultivated in Yunnan, China, using PCR markers corresponding to conserved motifs of disease resistance genes

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Many disease resistance genes in plants are found to have similar sequences that are presumably involved in pathogen recognition and signal transduction. This sequence conservation offers opportunities to develop markers that are indicative of function. Using polymerase chain reaction (PCR), primers can be designed to amplify sequences that correspond to conserved motifs of resistance genes. These PCR markers, called resistance gene analog (RGA) markers, have been used to characterize germplasm and breeding lines in barley, wheat, and rice (Chen et al 1998).

This study tested this approach to evaluate the diversity of a set of varieties from Yunnan Province, China. RGA markers were applied to analyze 41 modern rice varieties and landraces cultivated in Luxi county in Yunnan and to test the minimal number of primer combinations needed to reveal the informative relationship among varieties.

Rice genome DNA was extracted at Yunnan Agricultural University using mini-prep protocol (Zheng et al 1995). Molecular characterization was done at IRRI. The PCR primers were designed based on conserved motifs of disease resistance genes: leucine-rich repeats, nucleotide-binding site, and kinase of a broad collection of disease resistance genes (see table). Genomic DNA (20 ng) from each variety was PCR-amplified using a primer pair as described by Chen et al (1998). Each 25 µL reaction contains 50 mM KCl, 20 mM Tris-HCl, 5 mM MgCl₂, 0.2 mM of each dNTP, 60 ng of each primer, 20 ng template DNA, and 1 unit of Taq. The reaction was conducted using the following conditions: denature 5 min at 95 °C; 40 cycles of 1 min at 94 °C, 1 min at 45 °C, 2 min at 72 °C;

and a final extension of 7 min at 72 °C. Amplified fragments were separated by 4% polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis and silver-stained.

RGA banding patterns produced by each of the five primers revealed a high degree of intervarietal polymorphism. The composite banding patterns generated from all PCR primers were scored as binary data and analyzed using NTSYS version 1.8 (Exeter Software, Setauket, New York). Dice similarity coefficients were calculated to generate a dendrogram. Statistical stability of the branches in the cluster was estimated by bootstrap analysis with 2,000 replicates using the Winboot computer program (Yap and Nelson 1996). A consensus dendrogram based on markers generated from five primer pairs is shown in the figure.

Most of the branches had high bootstrap values, indicating the robustness of the branching pattern. The consensus dendrogram divided the Yunnan varieties into two groups corresponding to indica-japonica differentiation. With a few exceptions, modern and landrace varieties tended to form separate groupings. Lower bootstrap values were noted within the landrace group, suggesting that diversity within groups was higher among landraces. The degree of relatedness was higher among newly bred and released varieties. This may reflect the common pedigrees shared by improved varieties, e.g., Chujing and Hexi series of varieties. Three improved varieties—Chujing 14, Gangyou 12, and Xianyou 22—appear to be distinct from the others.

Primers used and the corresponding number of amplified and polymorphic bands generated.

Primer ^a	Sequence (5'3') ^b	Amplified bands	Polymorphic bands
XLRR for XLRR rev	CCG TTG GAC AGG AAG GAG CCC ATA GAC CGG ACT GTT	60	40
NLRR inv1 NLRR inv2	TGC TAC GTT CTC CGG G TGA GGC CGT GAA AAA TAT	74	59
LM637 LM638	ARI GCT ARI GGI ARI CC GGI GGI GTI GGI AAI ACI AC	55	43
S1 AS3	GGT GGG GTT GGG AAG ACA ACG IAG IGC IAG IGG IAG ICC	51	36
Pto kin1 Pto kin2	GCA TTG GAA CAA GGT GAA AGG GGG ACC ACC ACG TAG	51	38

^aThe primer pairs, XLRR for and XLRR rev and NLRR inv1 and NLRR inv2 were designed based on leucine-rich repeat regions of genes *Xa21* and *N* (N. Naqvi, IRRI). The primer pairs LM637 and LM638 and S1 and AS3 were designed based on the P-loop nucleotide-binding sites and LRR regions of genes *RPS2*, *N*, and *L6*. The primer pair Pto kin1 and Pto kin2 were designed based on the DNA sequence encoding for protein kinase in the tomato *Pto* gene conferring resistance to *Pseudomonas syringae* pv. *tomato*. All primers were made by GIBCO. ^bCodes for mixed bases: I = isonine, R = A/G. Degenerate primers were designed with isonine or more than one residue at the third codon position to fit the consensus amino acid sequence.

Dendrogram of 41 rice varieties based on polymorphic bands generated by five primer pairs. Numbers in branches indicate the percentage of times the group of lines in a branch occurred, based on 2,000 cycles in bootstrap analysis using the Winboot program.

Similarity matrices generated by different combinations of primers using MXCOMP program in NTSYS-pc were used to determine the minimal primer combinations needed to obtain a good assessment of the genetic relationship among rice varieties. Matrix comparison was conducted by pooling data in a stepwise manner (e.g., comparing the matrix produced by five primer pairs with matrices from combinations of two, three, and four primer pairs). Matrix comparison showed that the similarity matrix produced by three primer pairs was correlated (0.87–0.97) with that generated by five primer pairs (data not shown). The result suggests that using three primer pairs can provide

a quick assessment of genetic diversity.

Since RGA polymorphic markers may reflect diversity in domains of resistance genes, observed varietal groups may have different spectra of disease resistance. There has been a growing interest in increasing the level of genetic diversity in modern agricultural systems to sustain productivity. This approach is based on the premise that greater diversity in an agroecosystem would provide greater buffering capacity against biotic and abiotic stresses. The diversity information will be used to test whether mixing varieties that are agronomically similar but functionally diverse in disease resistance would provide enhanced protection against blast in the field.

References

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